

Affective Correlates to Emoticons on Visual E-Commerce and E-Learning Webpages

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Abstract:

Recent research shows that the concept of integrating affective systems into dynamic control models has its origin in Newtonian mechanics where it is possible to derive computational models on emotional response predictions based on physical phenomena. The engineering disciplines and the evolution rule of dynamic systems are based on an implicit relation that mostly gives the state of the system for a while into the future in the form of a third order differential equation. Identifying the state for all affected states in a control loop requires iterating the relation among user attributes several times to give a custom definition to every novel state model. This paper presents a novel method of integrating the affect state of users to a parallel control motor dynamics with a state-space procedure to predict the emotional response of users to e-learning and e-commerce webpages and its correlates to emotional emoticons on webpages. There were three (3) modules to approach this: (1) conduct a brief literature review on dynamic control systems (2) define a state-space system that holds all user attributes (2) make predictions on affect state by the representation of user emotion to emotional emoticons. (4) convey emotional emoticons on visual fixation locations through mapping schematics. The process enables the development of Artificial intelligence (AI) analytics that interpret user emotions on visual interfaces.

Keywords: Parallel Dynamic Control, User affect state, Physiological response, Artificial Intelligence, Emotional response, Fixation locations

1 Introduction

In the theory behind most control motor dynamics, the integration of other systems is done in a parallel processing scheme, the systems under study are known approximately and the parameters of the system are sometimes not known precisely. Most approximations bring the validity and relevance of the numerical solutions. The notions of stability have been introduced in dynamic systems, such as the structural stability of the system and there is a class of models and initial conditions that equals the trajectories of the systems. The trajectories are important in terms of their periodic and different states of the system. The applications of these models often require enumerating the classes and maintaining the system within one class to the classification of all possible predefined trajectories. The parallel dynamic procedure is systems that have two or more numbers defining the state and these states are predefined, the behaviour of the trajectories is set as a function of the user attributes that are required for the system application. The parameter varies in the dynamic systems and has divergence points where the quantified state of the behaviour

process changes with time. The schematic integration of the parallel systems to the affect state forms a convolutional network that integrates the physiological attributes of users by classifying emotional response correlates to emotional emoticons.

The globalised system forms an emotion inference engine that refers to the experience of feeling underlying the affective state of users. This represents the psycho-physiological phenomena that are represented in a 2D-dimensional model with both affect and emotional states. The valence is positivity to the negative evaluation of the current state of a user which is expressed as “*stress*”, “*relaxed*” and “*neutral*” emotion. This emotion is formed as a control system that includes several other predefined user parameters, such as the response peak, amplitude, magnitude, and pupil changes that form the data model. The parallel dynamic motor control forms the affective computational that can recognise, interpret, process, and also simulate the human affect states. One of the main objectives of the paper is to integrate the models by simulating the empathy that interprets the emotional state of the users as it is conveyed on the visual web interface.

$$f(x) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{dx}{dt} = Fx(t) + Gu(t) + \tilde{K}w(t) \\ y(t) = Hx(t) + Du(t) + w(t) \\ x(0) = x_0 \end{array} \right\} \quad (1)$$

Where the data models F, G, H , and D contain elements with the physical significance for the user attributes on a parallel scale with x_0 as the initial state of the data model. The relationship between the discrete state-space matrixes or data models A, B, C, D and \tilde{K} integrated with the continuous-time state-space matrices F, G, H, D and K are written in Equation 2 as:

$$\begin{aligned} A &= e^{FT}; \\ B &= \int_0^T e^{F\gamma} G d\gamma \\ C &= H; \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

These integrations assume that the input parameters are informed by a piece-wise constant over time intervals: $\tilde{K}T \leq t \leq (\tilde{K} + 1)T$. The exact relationship between the elements \tilde{K} is complex, but for short sampling intervals T , the following model equation can approximate the control module.

$$\int_0^T e^{F\gamma} \tilde{K} d\gamma \quad (3)$$

The resultant response model is stated as a transfer function in a linear scheme generalised model as:

$$y = Gu + He \quad (4)$$

The predicted response model (Equation 4) is mapped to emotional emoticons on the visual webpages.

2 Literature Review

One of the most useful ways of building emotion recognition systems is through affect computing, a definite way of modeling computational procedures by affective computing [Calvo and D’Mello (2010); Cowie et al. (2001a); Picard (2000b); Mollahosseini et al. (2017); Kim et al. (2004)] on human-computer interaction where the device can detect and appropriately respond to users’ emotional state and other visual stimuli [Brave and Nass (2007); Hibbeln et al. (2017); Esposito et al. (2015); Pantic and Rothkrantz (2003); Picard (2000a)]. A complex computational method with the ability to adapt can gather cues to user emotion from a variety of sources, such a method can include facial expressions, gestures, postures, keystrokes, skin temperature changes, and pupil response. The users’ attributes signify changes in users’ emotional state and these can be detected and interpreted by a computer. An embedded camera can capture images of the user and algorithms are then used to process the data to produce meaningful information [Wolf et al. (2002); Rinner and Wolf (2008); Bramberger et al. (2006); Quaritsch et al. (2007); Kryjak et al. (2018); Humenberger et al. (2010); Bravo et al. (2011); Wu and Aghajan (2008)]. Other emotional recognition models include gesture and speech recognition. The basics of recognising emotional information require the extraction of meaningful patterns from the data that has been gathered. Sometimes these process is done using machine learning and deep learning techniques that process different modalities of information such as natural language process, speech recognition, and facial expression detection [Abdullah et al. (2021); Latha and Priya (2016); Zhang et al. (2023); Dixit and Kasbe (2020); Akccay and Ouguz (2020); Hema and Marquez (2023); Hassouneh et al. (2020); Tzirakis et al. (2017)].

The design of computational devices has made it possible to model and create emotion in machines that propose to exhibit innate emotional competencies that are capable of convincingly simulating emotions. A more practical approach is its technological capabilities to simulate emotional conversational agents to enrich and facilitate interactivity between the user and the machine. These human emotions are often associated with different surges in the hormonal paradigm of the cells in the body which are mostly measured by biometric tools. These affect states are also associated with the abstract states that are associated with the progress or lack of progress in an autonomous learning system. The affective emotional states correlate with time-derivatives and the learning curves of the learning system [Baker et al. (2013); Joffily and Coricelli (2013); Cowie et al. (2001b); Kerkeni et al. (2019); Greeley et al. (2007)] .

The papers derive a custom way of detecting emotion and at the same convey this emotion on the visual stimuli such as the webpages (E-learning and E-commerce) sites. The control motor dynamics of the system are used to predict the emotions for the user attributes and correlate them to emotional emoticons by fixation mappings to the visual interface. The proceeding section discusses the methods and procedures for the results obtained.

Figure 1: Framework for the affective machine and correlates to emotional emoticons to visual stimuli.

3 Method

This initial stage of the project is to design the control motor dynamic based on the state-space models discussed in the introductory section this is used to predict the emotional response and affect the state of the users. The second stage was conducting an experimental setup where ten participants were invited to interact with webpage stimuli based online. The simple stimuli involve the E-learning and E-commerce website and the rationale for using such webpages is based on the fact that the sites are usually frequented by users and the emotional response of the users is usually intensified with product search and study sessions. The participants were simply asked to interact with the products and course content load by looking through significant sections of the websites. Their physiological response was measured (Skin conductance response, Skin temperature, Pupil response, and Fixation location) and served as the input parameters. The framework in Figure 1 is used to detect users' affect state by correlating the user response or physiological response to the visual stimuli. This is mapped to the emoticons on the webpages and we can visualise the simulated response state of the users to the product they purchase and the course content they viewed.

Integrating the control systems makes for a tuned state of the model that specifies the performance and robustness of the model such as the reliability and model accuracy. The proposed model is developed using Matlab with controls that allow for capturing the basic objectives that are suitable for fast automated tuning. The libraries include standard control objectives with reference for tracking, disturbance rejection, and stability margins. The proceeding sections discuss results obtained from the experimental setup and model integration.

4 Result

The emotional emoticons were customised 3D modules designed using the virtual reality control libraries in Matlab. To set the correlates which input time interval is to set a short-term time frame since optimal response peaks and phase changes can be detected at every timestamp. The optimal response peak was only selected at the initial stage and with this is mapped to an emotional response of the user. For instance, if the user is detected to be relaxed, the optimal tonic phase is less than the baseline and this is mapped to a smiling emoji (Figure 2). The control motor dynamics classified the affect state as stressed, relaxed, and neutral. Neutral emoticons (Figure 3) are usually found to be contradictory because of the color change and are usually mapped outside the visual space.

The error can also be controlled by the error rejection state of the dynamic control systems. The controls are initially set to display the original fixation locations from the experimental study and the predicted state is mapped as the emoticons on the webpages. Normally using an eye tracker can only display fixation points or gaze points but doesn't tell us much about the user's emotional state. The novel method here is to correlate user emotional responses to gaze points in the form of emoticons which are conveyed to the visual interface. As a form of analytical tool, one can load the webpage address and visualise the simulated gaze points and emoticons on the webpages, the display of emotional emoticons also add-ons to the schematic visual aesthetics of the pages, which can be viewed by users and evaluators and more approachable than subjective views of the users. The model framework also provides the capability to visualise model performance and reliability.

Figure 2: Visual interface of the E-learning website with fixation locations and mapped emotional emoticons correlates to affect state.

Figure 4 shows the window output for the performance of the state-space model, the input parameters are the Skin conductance response, skin temperature, fixation location (mapped fixation on the Y coordinate, and the pupil response). The sample time is based on 0.08 seconds of the free parameters A, B, C , and D . The reaction to stimuli i.e. the time it takes for an emotional response to be detected depends on the stimulus onset and the third-order differential equation and adopts an error rejection rate which can automatically ignore noise and anomalies. The performance rate is set as $0.11e^{04}\%$ and less than the estimated 0.01% , this is feasible for user behaviour data. The discrete time-variant model (dynamic control model) is also robust and resistant to an error on a large-scale data containing web address, fixation location, keystrokes, and mouse clicks integrated into the physiological response. The model and its framework are a prototypical representation of the model and optimisation procedures will be part of future schemes.

Figure 3: Visual interface with mapped neutral mood emoticons and fixation locations on E-commerce website.

5 Conclusion

The paper investigates the procedures in parallel control dynamics for user affective correlates to emoticons on visual E-Commerce and E-Learning, the paper presents a novel method of integrating the affect state of users to a parallel control motor dynamics with a state-space procedure to predict the emotional response to users to e-learning and e-commerce webpages and its correlates to emotional emoticons on webpages. There were three basic modules to approach this such as conducting a brief literature review on dynamic control systems, defining a state-space system that holds all user attributes, making predictions on affect state by a representation of user emotion to emotional emoticons, and conveying emotional emoticons on visual fixation locations through mapping schematics. The process enables the development of Artificial intelligence (AI) analytics that interpret user emotions on visual interfaces. The parallel schematics assigned to the dynamic control are robust with error rejection capabilities that detect the emotional response of users at the emotional emoji correlates. Future work would be to determine the process of the system modification by optimising the process and comparing it with physical dynamic control models with auto-deep learning procedures.

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Figure 4: Systems performance information for input parameters and the order of differential equation for the dynamic model.

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